

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH OF THE SCO COUNTRIES: SYNERGY AND INTEGRATION

上合组织国家的科学研究：协同和一体化

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这些会议文结合了会议的材料 – 研究论文和科学工作者的论文报告。它考察了职业化人格的技术和社会学问题。一些文章涉及人格职业化研究问题的理论和方法论方法和原则。

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外国直接投资对东道国经济影响的评估模型分析
**ANALYSIS OF MODELS FOR ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF
FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT ON THE HOST ECONOMY**

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摘要。几十年来，外国直接投资（FDI）及其影响一直是世界经济中热门的研究课题，这一事实证实了该主题的相关性。有许多实证和数学研究评估了 FDI 对东道国经济的影响。已经研究了 FDI 对东道国经济吸收能力的影响的依赖性。评估 FDI 对接受国经济影响的研究的主要目的是系统化可用的方法。基于国内外科学家的研究，对现有模型进行了比较分析，揭示了它们的优缺点。获得的结果将允许选择更有效的工具来评估 FDI 对东道国经济的潜在影响。

关键词：计量经济学建模、外国直接投资、评估 FDI 影响的模型。

Abstract. *The relevance of the topic is confirmed by the fact that foreign direct investment (FDI) and its effects have been a popular subject of research in the world economy for several decades. There are many empirical and mathematical studies assessing the impact of FDI on the host economy. The dependence of the effects of FDI on the absorption capacity of host economies has been investigated. The main purpose of the research on assessing the impact of FDI on the recipient country's economy is to systematize the available approaches. Based on the works of foreign and domestic scientists, a comparative analysis of existing models has been carried out, their advantages and disadvantages have been revealed. The results obtained will allow choosing more effective tools for assessing the potential impact of FDI on the host economy.*

Keywords: *econometric modeling, foreign direct investment, models for assessing the impact of FDI.*

Introduction

In modern conditions of rapidly growing globalization, sustainable economic development of any country is impossible without its participation in world eco-

conomic relations. An important form of economic cooperation between states is investment exchange, in particular foreign direct investment (FDI).

The economic literature provides the following definition of the concept of foreign direct investment: “Foreign direct investment is the investment of foreign entrepreneurial capital in the production of material and other assets, in the construction of new factories and branches of foreign companies, in the acquisition of existing enterprises through the purchase of majority stakes” [1].

Based on this definition, we can conclude that the influx of FDI contributes to the growth of capital investments, ensures the stability of the investment process, promotes the development of innovation and a favorable investment environment, growth in employment and labor productivity, production, and renewal of fixed assets. It is important that through FDI one can gain access to foreign technologies. Even if these technologies are not cutting-edge, they can be disruptive for host economies, industries and specific enterprises.

In modern conditions of a high degree of depreciation of fixed assets of domestic enterprises, attracting FDI can be called a vital factor for the development of the Russian economy. FDI contributes to the creation of new production capacities or increases the demand for existing ones. In addition, attracting foreign capital is one of the main sources of innovative development of the economy, since it not only contributes to the introduction of technological innovations and ensuring sustainable economic growth for the host economy, but also brings new knowledge and innovative production technologies. Researchers believe that technology exchange leads to an increase in the technological level and qualifications of personnel in the investment-receiving industry. This is the most obvious positive effect of FDI [2]. Improving the qualifications of personnel becomes a real stimulus for the growth of specialists’ wages and the development of scientific and technological progress in the host country [3, 4].

However, attracting FDI may also entail negative consequences, for example, on the balance of payments, replacing profits with FDI or due to the use of profit sheltering schemes. There are frequent cases of suppression of local producers, their purchase in order to eliminate competitors. It is also impossible to exclude the risks of transferring “dirty industries” to the country, transferring low-skilled industries, low-paid jobs and discarding obsolete equipment for the production of products that are already approaching the last stage of their life cycle [5]. Unhealthy institutional and economic environments are also barriers to attracting FDI. This is one of the reasons for the lack of the expected positive effect from attracting FDI [6].

Along with direct effects, FDI also has an indirect impact on the host economy through the economic environment, institutions, and third parties. For example, the presence of foreign firms in an industry affects the productivity of domestic

firms. The nature of this impact, like direct effects, can be both positive and negative.

The multidirectional nature of the impact of FDI on the economy of the recipient country is confirmed by a comparison of many studies conducted by economists in different countries at different times. Much of the research devoted to studying the consequences of attracting foreign capital to a country or industry and assessing the effects of FDI uses econometric modeling. Many methodologies have been developed to assess the impact of FDI on the host economy, both at the country and regional level, and at the sector or firm level [7].

A comparison of the main types of these models will make it possible to understand which tools for assessing the expected effect of FDI on the host economy should be chosen in a given case.

Literature review

Interest in the impact of FDI on the host economy dates back to the 1960s. Beginning with the work of R. Vernon, published in 1966, research on this topic has become the basis of theoretical and methodological principles for organizing and optimizing the effective process of attracting and using foreign capital.

Half a century of research has examined various aspects of FDI and its impact on the host economy. FDI theories were constantly created and developed, for example, such as the theory of internationalization, the Flying Geese paradigm, OLI and IDP theories (R. Vernon, S. Hymer, Ch. Kindleberger, F. Nickerbocker, E. Graham, P. J. Buckley, M. Casson, K. Akamatsu, K. Kojima, T. Ozawa, M. Porter, J. Dunning).

External effects were assessed in developed countries (R. Caves, S. Globerman, V. Aitken, S. Girma, R Griffith), in developing countries (M. Blömstroem, A. Kokko, V. Altken), in transition economies (C M. Kadochnikov, S. Dyankov, Y. Kinoshita); the dependence of these effects on the ability of host companies to absorb these investments and on the level of the technological gap was assessed (A. Kokko, R. Fmdlay). A lot of research on the nature of the influence of FDI has made it possible to identify the negative (R. Caves, S. Globerman, H. Hien) and positive aspects of both direct and indirect effects of foreign investment (A. Kokko, P. Egger, S. Djankov, P.J. Buckley).

Many articles are devoted to assessing the effect of foreign direct investment in different countries. Basically, these works assess the impact of foreign capital on labor productivity or economic growth in the recipient country, since the impact of FDI on these indicators is obvious [8].

Most studies of this nature are devoted to assessing the impact of FDI on the productivity of local firms receiving these investments. In models of this type, the dynamics of the productivity of local companies is studied, various tests are carried out regarding the “spill-over” of technologies and the involvement or dis-

placement of domestic companies in the host industry and in related industries (B. Aitken, A. Harrison, J. Buckley, S. Dimelis, H. Louri, N. Ponomareva, N.Yu Melentyeva [9]). Along with them, models for assessing technological exchange (K. Ramanathan, G. Blalock, P.J. Gertler) and spillover effects (H. Görg, E. Strobl, E.A. Fedorova [10]) are being developed. The impact of FDI in these types of models is assessed at the industry or firm level.

Models have also been developed to estimate the impact of FDI on economic growth rates. Models of this type analyze the nature of the impact of foreign capital on the socio-economic development of the host country (V.V. Leontiev, R. Welfens, R. Jasinski, E.V. Balatsky), that is, such models assess the impact of FDI at the macroeconomic level.

Russian economists have more than once in their research turned to comparing models assessing the impact of FDI on economic growth in order to identify their advantages and disadvantages. This kind of research was carried out, for example, by E.V., Balatsky, I.V. Degtyareva, O.V. Gordyachkova, M.P. Boldurina [11].

Methods

The study is based on the study of the works of foreign and domestic authors in the field of developing models for assessing the impact of foreign direct investment on the economy of the host country. During the research process, methods such as comparative, logical, monographic, analysis and synthesis were used.

Results

Based on the above studies, a comparative table of models for assessing the impact of FDI on economic growth rates was compiled (see Table 1).

Table 1

Comparison of models for assessing the impact of FDI on economic growth rates

Name	Description	Results	Flaws
“Differential model of intercountry redistribution of capital by V. Leontiev” [12]	Models the economies of developed and developing countries. In the bloc of developed countries, the principles of multiplier and accelerator work. The flow of FDI comes from developed countries to developing countries and directly affects economic growth in developing countries	According to V. Leontiev’s calculations, the growth rate of GNP of developing countries would be comparable to the growth rate of developed countries if capital were transported 5 times more than the actual value [13]	1) the condition of direct dependence of capital imports and the rate of economic growth is impossible, because the process of import and export of capital occurs simultaneously 2) a careful, technically complex classification of countries into groups of developed and developing is required. 3) the structure of foreign capital is not taken into account

			<p>4) regression functions based on dynamic series are not suitable for transition economies</p> <p>5) the need for a significant amount of national and international statistics</p>
<p>“Model of economic growth” Welfens-Jasinski [14]</p>	<p>The model is based on production functions. It estimates the potential growth of production when the volume of capital imports increases by a given amount (Dyatereva, 2006). Features of the model include the fact that it was developed for transitional economies, and that it takes into account the pace of scientific and technological progress (STP)</p>	<p>Due to the complexity and labor intensity, there are no studies using this model [15]</p>	<p>1) The time lag required for the development of technologies is not taken into account</p> <p>2) double accounting of investments in fixed assets and in national statistics of the growth of domestic fixed capital.</p> <p>3) the complexity of calculating the pace of scientific and technical progress</p> <p>4) the need for a good statistical base, long retrospective time series, which is very difficult to obtain in developing countries</p>
<p>Model of interaction between domestic and foreign investments “predator-prey”</p>	<p>Based on the construction of economic dependencies between indicators of investment activity of two sectors: local firms and enterprises with the participation of foreign capital</p>	<p>The interaction of foreign and domestic companies has a positive effect on economic growth. By checking the fulfillment of this condition, it is possible to determine the effectiveness of the sectoral structure of the national economy</p>	<p>1) Labor intensity due to non-linear dependencies,</p> <p>2) a good statistical database is required,</p> <p>3) FDI is reflected indirectly in the model.</p> <p>4) Basically, the models are based on production connections between sectors of the economy, and not on the investment process</p>
<p>Difference model of multiplier-accelerator</p>	<p>The rate of economic growth depends on investment activity, the share of FDI and the return from them in the foreign and local sectors</p>	<p>Calculations by Balatsky and Pavlichenko showed that the share of FDI in the total volume of capital investments of over 18.87% will be critical until the share of FDI reaches this value, the industries will maintain high production returns. Calculations by Zelenskaya and Preobrazhensky</p>	<p>1) It is necessary to have certain series of data on the volume of FDI, the volume of output in two sectors at comparable prices. This requires careful and labor-intensive work with data.</p> <p>2) the assumption of an instantaneous change in the initial share of FDI is not fulfilled in practice</p> <p>3) the accelerator values are unstable, especially for transition economies and economies that have</p>
<p>Modified difference model of the multiplier – accelerator [16]</p>	<p>The model is based on the principle of calculating the dynamic investment multiplier (marginal productivity of investment). The rate of economic growth depends on the same indicators</p>		

	showed that in 2009 the critical point was at 14.6% [17,18]	experienced a crisis [16]
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Source: compiled by the author based on research [12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18].

More often than others, the multiplier-accelerator difference model, modified by E. Balatsky and R. Pavlichenko, is used for econometric calculations, since it is more convenient and easier to calculate in comparison with other models. However, modern macroeconomic instability does not allow ensuring the condition of equality of investment and savings in conditions of macroeconomic equilibrium, which complicates the correct use of the model.

Models that estimate the impact of FDI on productivity are simpler than “macroeconomic” ones, and therefore are very popular among economists. The main idea of such studies is to see whether the productivity of national companies increases due to foreign capital injections [19].

In studies using econometric models of this type, often, along with the direct impact of FDI on productivity, indirect effects are also assessed, such as demonstration and imitation, the effect of competition, training, and the effect of foreign connections. The impact of foreign presence on the productivity of local firms through demonstration and imitation, labor mobility, competition, connections [20]. These are the so-called spillover effects, which can be defined as the “flow” of technologies and production methods from foreign firms to domestic firms receiving FDI and domestic firms not receiving FDI.

Despite a significant period of time and a fairly large number of studies devoted to this topic, the nature of the impact of FDI on the host economy in developing countries cannot be determined unambiguously. The summary table below of a number of studies shows that in different countries over different periods of time, investment had both positive and negative effects, and in some countries there was no effect of foreign presence at all (see Table 2).

The positive effects of FDI are expressed not only in increased labor productivity, but also contribute to GDP growth, exports, and employment growth, especially among highly qualified personnel. Most of the negative effects of FDI are associated with the destructive influence of international corporations on the structure of the national economy and labor market [24]. This is manifested through greatly increased competition, increased income differentiation, and decreased productivity in firms that do not receive direct investment. These effects are especially clearly visible in the short term.

Discussion

The phenomenon of FDI itself is quite difficult to describe and evaluate; it has a diverse and diversified nature of influence on the host economy; accordingly, the

decision to attract foreign investment in a particular industry must be balanced, taken on the basis of an assessment of both positive effects and negative consequences, therefore quantitative assessments of this influence, taking into account all factors and consequences are still relevant [16].

The analysis of the research carried out in this work showed that two approaches to quantifying external effects from FDI can be distinguished: models that assess the impact of FDI on economic growth rates and on productivity in local companies receiving foreign investment.

Models that assess the impact of FDI at the macroeconomic level allow us to determine the contribution of FDI to macroeconomic indicators and the level of transnationalization of the economy. However, such models are complex, require certain data series and have a number of disadvantages, which explains their rare use by economists in their research.

Table 2
Studies assessing the impact of FDI on productivity

Nature of influence	Authors	Year	Country	Period
Positive	Kokko et al.	1994 1996	Mexico, Uruguay	1970, 1988
	Egger et al.	2001	Austria	1981-1994
	Djankov, Hoekman	2000	Czech	1992-1996
	Ghatak, Halicioglu	2006	Using the example of 140 countries	1991-2001
	Fu, Balasubramanyam	2005	China	1987-1998
	Hunya, Geishecker	2005	Using the example of 27 countries	1993-2007
	Buckley et al.	2007	China	1995-1999
	Akulava, Vakhitova	2010	Ukraine	2001-2007
	Takii	2011	Indonesia	1990-2003
	Xu, Sheng	2012	China	2000-2003
	Dua, Harrison, Jefferson	2012	China	1998-2007
Farahani, Sadr, Hossein	2013	Middle Eastern countries	1999-2010	
Negative	Caves	1974	Canada, Australia	1965-1967, 1962-1966
	Globerman	1979	Canada	1972
	Hthin Hien	2019	Vietnam	2011-2015

Has no effect	Blomstrom, Persson	1983	Mexico	1970
	Haddad, Harrison	1993	Morocco	1985-89
	Hisarckilar et al.	2006	Algeria, Egypt, Cyprus, Morocco, Israel, Syria, Türkiye, Tunisia, Jordan	1970-2003
	Faras, Ghali	2009	UAE, Saudi Arabia, Oman, Qatar, Kuwait, Bahrain	1970-2006
	Azman-Saini, Baharumshah, Law	2010	Using the example of 85 countries	1976-2004
	Dimelis, Papaioannou	2010	Using the example of 42 countries	1993-2001
	Zukowska-Gagelmann	2000	Poland	1993-1997
Ambiguous	Girma et al.	2001	England	1991-1996
	Kholdy	1995	Mexico, Brazil, Chile, Singapore, Zambia	1970-1990
	Aitken, Harrison	1999	Venezuela	1979-1989
	Zhou et al.	2002	China	1992-1995
	Dimelis, Louri	2001	Greece	
	Anwar, Nguyen	2011	Vietnam	1990-2007
	Waldkirch, Ofosu	2008	Ghana	1991-1997

Source: compiled by the author based on research [19, 21, 22, 23]

Models estimating the impact of foreign direct investment on the productivity of enterprises or industries are widespread in the economic literature, covering different countries and different time periods. However, the results obtained by researchers are quite varied, which does not allow us to give an unambiguous answer about the nature of the influence of foreign capital on their host company, sector or industry.

It should be noted that in Russia insufficient attention is paid to studies of quantitative assessments of the impact of FDI on productivity and economic growth.

Conclusion

To summarize, it should be noted that, despite the wide geography and long period of active research devoted to the impact of foreign direct investment on the host economy, it is still not possible to accurately determine what benefits and what costs FDI brings to the recipient country. The analysis of the works of Russian and foreign economists allows us to draw only one general conclusion: foreign direct investment has a multidirectional impact on the national economy, therefore, in the economic literature there is not yet a comprehensive assessment of the results of attracting foreign investment into the economy.

The main reasons for this are. Firstly, the analysis of the costs and benefits of FDI seems quite complex in itself, since today there is no uniform approach

to the methodology for its implementation. Secondly, the fragmented results can be explained by the unavailability of the required data. For example, to assess productivity, indicators such as the number of employees in the enterprise, fixed capital, the share of foreign ownership in the enterprise, the volume of foreign direct investment, and the level of wages are used. Unfortunately, not all enterprises provide information of this nature in the public domain. Thirdly, the socio-economic conditions in host countries are not the same: unequal absorption capacity, level of human capital development, institutional environment, etc.

Obviously, it is necessary to continue working on this issue, studying and comparing various models for quantifying the effects of FDI in order to create a model that optimally describes those indicators of the host economy that will be influenced by the attraction of foreign capital.

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